

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Covid–19: Pandemic Risks and SMEs Sustainability in Developing Nations: Evidence from Nigeria

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Abstract

Due to the COVID–19 pandemic, several Small and Medium Scale Businesses have collapsed. This paper therefore examines COVID–19, risk management and SMEs sustainability in developing nations. The main objective of this paper is to suggest implementable risk management strategies that can help revamp the business operations of SMEs. The specific objectives are to ascertain the effect of COVID–19 on SMEs business operation; and to determine the role of effective risk management strategies in revamping SMEs business operation from COVID–19 pandemic. The study made use of cross-sectional design approach which recognises that data be collected at one time. The population of this study consists of all the small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Lagos State. Ordinary Least Square of Regression model was employed to test the hypotheses of this study. This paper revealed that COVID–19 has significant negative effects on SMEs business operation; effective risk management strategies such as risk avoidance, reduction, sharing and retention can play a significant role in revamping SMEs business operation from COVID–19 pandemic; and adequate financing can mitigate the negative effect of Covid–19 on SMEs business operations. Arisen from the analysis of the study, this study recommended that financial institutions should make more funds available to SMEs especially in the face of Covid–19 pandemic; and SMEs should employ effective risk management strategies such as risk avoidance, reduction, sharing and retention.

Keywords: COVID–19; Developing Nations; Risk Management; SMEs, Sustainability

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1.Introduction

Before the severe hit of COVID–19, small and medium scale enterprises have been playing a critical role in socio-economic transformation and development of any nation. They are regarded as veritable tool for job creation, income generation, capital savings, increased productivity, rapid industrialization, rural development, food security, poverty alleviation and regional balance (Agwu & Emeti, 2020). SMEs are also regarded as the single largest source of employment in economies and play key social inclusion role in strengthening stake holdings and voice in the economy (Mousley, 2017). In Nigeria, small and medium scale enterprises constitute more than 90 percent of the businesses (Gbandi & Amisah, 2020) and they are prevalent in virtually all the sectors of the Nigerian economy with a total number of 72,839 (SMEDAN & NBS, 2013). In Lagos

State alone, the number of SMEs is 11,663 (SMEDAN & NBS, 2013) which means that SMEs are essential to the achievement of socio-economic objectives in Nigeria and are poised to generate employment, create wealth and reduce the prevalence of poverty.

The coronavirus outbreak severely impacted SMEs business operations negatively and also ravaging human health, disrupting the livelihood of thousands of people, and impact negatively on the global economy (Craven, Liu, Mysore & Wilson, 2020). Chukwuka and Amare (2020) confirmed cases of the novel coronavirus named COVID–19, which was first reported in December 2019 in the Chinese Province of Hubei and declared a pandemic by the World Health Organization in March 2020 is now over 28 million worldwide, 1,344,403 in Africa and 55,829 in Nigeria as at September 2020. The presence of the virus in Nigeria was first reported on February 27, 2020, when an Italian citizen visiting Nigeria